

ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ВА ТУРКИЯ ҲАМКОРЛИГИНИНГ СТРАТЕГИК ЖИҲАТЛАРИ ВА ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада Туркия ва Ўзбекистон икки томонлама муносабатларининг шаклланиш босқичлари, иқтисодий, сиёсий, маданий ҳамда хавфсизлик соҳаларидаги ўзаро ҳамкорлик алоқаларининг натижалари ҳамда истиқболлари таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: Туркия, ташқи сиёсат, Ўзбекистон, ҳамкорлик, иқтисод, сиёсат, хавфсизлик.

СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА УЗБЕКИСТАНИ И ТУРЦИИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются этапы становления двусторонних отношений между Турцией и Узбекистаном, результаты и перспективы взаимного сотрудничества в экономической, политической, культурной сферах и сфере безопасности.

Ключевые слова: Турция, внешняя политика, Узбекистан, сотрудничество, экономика, политика, безопасность.

STRATEGIC ASPECTS AND PERSPECTIVES OF COOPERATION BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND TURKEY

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the stages of the formation of bilateral relations between Turkey and Uzbekistan, the results, and perspectives of cooperation in the economic, political, cultural, and security spheres.*

Keywords: *Turkey, foreign policy, Uzbekistan, cooperation, economy, politics, security.*

INTRODUCTION.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been significantly revitalizing its activities in multilateral cooperation formats, relying on new approaches to modern foreign policy. Turkey and Uzbekistan have a lot in common, from their geopolitical location and historical development to the uniqueness of the reforms they are currently undergoing. With its nearly 33 million inhabitants, geostrategic location, deep history, rich cultural values , and economic potential, Uzbekistan holds an important place for regional peace and stability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

Turkey attaches great importance to the development of cooperation with brotherly Uzbekistan in all fields and continues to strive for further development of the relations strengthened by close ties between the Turkish and Uzbek peoples. The new page that Turkey opens in this region, first of all with Uzbekistan, is important not only in terms of bilateral relations with this country but also in terms of regional and global balance and struggle for influence.

The common language, history, similar culture, and ethnic closeness of the peoples of Turkey and Uzbekistan is a strong foundation of friendly relations between the two countries. Diplomatic relations between Turkey and Uzbekistan

have further developed as the Turkish state was one of the first to recognize the independence of our country. Turkey played an important role in the integration of Uzbekistan into the international community. The 30 years after Uzbekistan's independence was marked by various ups and downs in Uzbek-Turkey relations. In the first years of independence, political and expert circles of Uzbekistan discussed the so-called “Turkish model” principle of state and society structure.

The First President of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, hoped that Ankara would become the most reliable partner and friend for the young independent country in the complex and new world system. Turkey was the first to recognize the independence of Uzbekistan on December 16, 1991. Initially, bilateral relations were established in a spirit of brotherhood and confidence-building measures were taken. In April 1992, the embassy of Turkey in Tashkent, and in January 1993, the embassy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Ankara started its activity. By 1996, the agreement "On Eternal Friendship and Cooperation" was signed between our countries.

Uzbekistan-Turkey relations have gone through various twists and turns over the past years. It is appropriate to analyze the period of development between the two countries in 2 stages. The reason is that researchers consider the period of political stagnation in Turkey-Uzbekistan relations from the end of the 90s to 2017. According to Turkish sources, opinions have been put forward that Uzbekistan became isolated by conducting a closed foreign policy after gaining independence. But in the first years of independence, it is appropriate to cite specific reasons for conducting a cautious policy.

In the first years of independence, under the leadership of Islam Karimov, the main directions of Uzbekistan's foreign policy were the preservation of sovereignty and independence, security, and the principles of non-alignment with military blocs. The security and stability of our country's borders were prioritized above all issues,

and internal and external policies were formed in this context. In particular, special attention was paid to keeping the civil war in Tajikistan, ethnic conflicts in Kyrgyzstan, and the conflict in Afghanistan on the southern border away from the country. First of all, he prioritized the goal of stability and state-building within the country.

The first serious crisis in the early years of independence was when the leader of the political opposition in Uzbekistan and his supporters were offered political asylum and refused to hand them over to Uzbekistan, which strained relations between the two countries. After this incident, about two thousand Uzbek students studying in Turkey were immediately returned to Uzbekistan. Differences between Turkey and Uzbekistan in this regard later became an open problem. After this first diplomatic blow, the head of state distanced Uzbekistan from any symbolic ideas of pan-Turkism and stopped participating in almost all meetings of the Turkic world.

Another crisis in Turkey-Uzbekistan relations occurred against the background of Andijan events in 2005. In May 2005, a group of armed men stormed a prison in Andijan, Uzbekistan, located in the restive Fergana region, and his home was raided by Uzbek security forces, causing international protests. Turkey supported the UN resolution on the human rights situation of the Karimov regime and accepted some restrictive measures adopted by the Council of the European Union against Uzbekistan. This action of Turkey caused protests on the side of Uzbekistan and canceled the visit of President Abdulla Gul to Tashkent. Agreements in the military sphere were also canceled. This crisis was evaluated as the biggest crisis in the relations between the two countries and caused a long political stagnation in the following years.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS.

Uzbekistan is one of the ancient capitals with a rich cultural heritage for the Turkish and Islamic world. Uzbekistan, which has the largest population in Central Asia, has long been regarded as a country with which no contact can be established for Turkey. However, the official visit of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to Turkey on October 25-27, 2017 started a new era of cooperation and friendship between Turkey and Uzbekistan. This visit was the first visit of a high-ranking Uzbek leader to Turkey since 1999. During the talks held during the visit, issues of development of cooperation between Uzbekistan and Turkey in political, trade-economic, investment, transport-communication, agriculture, transport, tourism, science, and other fields were discussed in detail.

The new mechanisms established between Turkey and Uzbekistan indicate that relations have risen to the level of strategic partnership. Since that date, significant changes have taken place in the relations between the two countries, especially in the economic sphere. Uzbekistan is the second largest economy in the region after Kazakhstan. With more than thirty million inhabitants, market potential, geographical location in the center of Central Asia, rich natural resources, military power, long history, and rich cultural values, Uzbekistan has great potential to become a leading country in the region. Cooperation with Uzbekistan in all fields has always been promising for Turkey. Turkey's geographic location as a strategic hub between Central Asia and the European Union provides an important opportunity for landlocked Uzbekistan to diversify trade along the Western Energy Corridor, and Turkey's entry into the EU markets has attracted the interest of Central Asian countries, including Uzbekistan. The Turkey-Uzbekistan Business Council was established in 1993, and more than 90 bilateral agreements and protocols were signed in various fields from 1992-2019 to form the legal basis of relations.

DISCUSSIONS.

Today, Turkey has become the third largest economic partner of Uzbekistan. The volume of economic relations between Turkey and Uzbekistan reached three billion dollars. It is planned to increase this number to 5 billion dollars in the next 5 years and to 10 billion dollars in the next 10 years. Currently, about 500 Turkish firms and companies are operating in Uzbekistan in the fields of construction, textiles, food, hotel services, construction materials, medicine, and plastics, 100 of which are representative offices.

The countries are also strengthening cooperation in the field of transport and communication. In this regard, the Navoi-Turkmanbashi-Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway, which connects the railways of Turkmenistan, Azerbaijan, and Georgia with the Turkish transport network, is of great importance for Uzbekistan. Through the Turkish port of Mersin, this railway gives Uzbekistan access to the Mediterranean Sea. In order to increase the transit potential of this transport corridor, the parties are currently working on the issues of customs-tax policy coordination and simplification of the customs process. In this regard, a comprehensive plan for 2018-2022 was established by Mirziyov's order, which allows for the modernization of Uzbekistan's transport infrastructure, diversification of goods transit and foreign trade routes.

Turkey and Uzbekistan also cooperate on the issue of Afghanistan. After the withdrawal of US troops from Afghanistan, a new situation has arisen for both Afghanistan and the region. The security of Central Asian countries, especially Uzbekistan, is directly related to the current situation in Afghanistan. Uzbekistan participates in the "Heart of Asia - Istanbul Process" platform organized under the leadership of Turkey in order to solve the problem of Afghanistan. The establishment of stable stability in Afghanistan is very important for both Turkey

and Central Asian countries. In this framework, Turkey works together with the countries of the region and Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION.

In short, since 2017, relations between Turkey and Uzbekistan have acquired a strategic direction, and their mutually beneficial cooperation has risen to the level of strategic partnership. The level of mutual trust and support of the parties serves as the basis for strategic cooperation between the two countries. From this point of view, the establishment of a strategic partnership allows Turkey and Uzbekistan to coordinate their actions on important issues of international relations. As a result of fundamental changes in the international system, new opportunities and problems arise. It is these opportunities and challenges that affect the general character of interstate relations. Ongoing events are influencing the dynamics shaping Turkey's Central Asia policy. From this point of view, it is possible to see how a regional policy strategically oriented towards Central Asia is being built. As a result of its strategic location, Central Asia has a direct impact on changes in global relations. As a result, this region is becoming increasingly important in the context of international structural transformations.

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